

THE PRIMES IN THE SMARANDACHE SYMMETRIC SEQUENCE

Maohua Le

Department of Mathematics, Zhanjiang Normal College
Zhanjiang, Guangdong, P.R.China.

Abstract. Let $S = \{s_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be the Smarandache symmetric sequence. In this paper we prove that if n is an even integer and $n/2 \not\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then s_n is not a prime.

Let $S = \{s_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be the Smarandache symmetric sequence, where

$$(1) \quad s_1=1, s_2=11, s_3=121, s_4=1221, s_5=12321, s_6=123321, \\ s_7=1234321, s_8=12344321, \dots$$

Smarandache asked how many primes are there among S ? (See [1, Notions 3]). In this paper we prove the following result:

Theorem. If n is an even integer and $n/2 \not\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then s_n is not a prime.

Proof. If n is an even integer, then $n=2k$, where k is a positive integer. We see from (1) that

$$(2) \quad s_n = \overline{12 \dots kk \dots 21}$$

It implies that

$$(3) \quad s_n = 1 \cdot 10^{t_1} + 2 \cdot 10^{t_2} + \dots + k \cdot 10^{t_k} + k \cdot 10^{t_{k+1}} + \dots + 2 \cdot 10^{t_{2k-1}} + 1 \cdot 10^{t_{2k}},$$

where t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2k} are nonnegative integers. Since $10^t \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ for any nonnegative integer t , we get from (3) that

$$(4) \quad s_n \equiv 1 + 2 + \dots + k + k + \dots + 2 + 1 \equiv k(k+1) \pmod{3}.$$

If $k \not\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then either $k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ or $k \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

In both cases, we have $k(k+1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $3 \mid s_n$ by (4).

Thus, s_n is not a prime. The theorem is proved.

Reference

1. Dumitrescu and Seleacu, Some Notions and Questions In Number Theory, Erhus Univ. Press, Glendale, 1994.